

DEVELOPMENT OF A PLAN FOR THE CREATION OF THE 20 SUPERVERSES

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Abstract: With new mathematics, where there will be no limit tending to zero, we are equipped to make the indicative equations-molds of creation of the 20 super-universes, without decay there. We achieve the avoidance of decay because we have diagnosed that it entered our universes, with an incomplete radial oscillation of the charged opposite particles of the atom and the incomplete infinite series that does not equal its sum to the unit and reduces the energy of atoms.

We moderate the equations of the harmonic oscillation. And the 20 superverses will have only harmonic oscillations.

The equations molded into the creation of universes are illustrative, and these universes will take thousands of years to form. Their atoms, were already created.

Keywords: 20 super-universes, harmonic oscillation, energy of atoms.

1. INTRODUCTION

My worldview accepts that creation by the personal female Zero and male Zero is not complete. The female created six universes, whose holographs are located on cube chairs, surrounding the bubble of the control center. These universes exist in the three dimensions of space and one super-dimension of time. He also created six other universes of the same dimensions, whose holographs are located on the faces of a regular hexahedron surrounding the central bubble (triangular cone with its opposite cone).

The male god created 12 super-universes, the holographs of which are located in the dodecahedron seats.

We will draw up a plan of 20 superverses, the holographs of which will be located in the seats of a regular twentyhedron.

You should read THE COMPLETION OF GREATION¹ and THE OVERTURNING OF INFINIMATESIMAL CALCULUS² and here you will be given the bases of new applied mathematics, calculus of differences. The theory of simple harmonic oscillation will also be given.

Mathematics, the mathematical formulas of physics, was used by the gods as molds for the creation of universes. So will we.

2. METHODOLOGY

Just as the ancient Greek philosophers set the principles to build their theories, so here we set the principles.

Epicurus and Democritus set as principles atoms (complete) and emptiness, Anaxagoras posited the infinite division of matter, etc.

Here, principles are set forth as the pre-existence of a higher impersonal reality, the absolute Zero, which partially transmuted into a male Zero face and at the same time the female Zero person was shelf-born. These are principles, and they have a logical basis, if you think about it.

The male and female as persons, invent ideas and design and create.

They create the universes mentioned above and use principles that we accept in our theory. They create universes with atoms, little indivisible hydrogen atoms.

A reflection in applied mathematics is that there is no limit tending to zero, ($\lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} (dx/dt) = v$). But there is $\Delta t \neq 0$ and $\Delta x/\Delta t = v$. This overturns calculus that was considered applied mathematics and establishes discrete mathematics.

At the same time, the laws of logic, especially inductive and deductive reasoning, are used here.

THE NEW MATHEMATICS

$$\text{Εχόμε } y = x_i + vt, \quad \Delta y = v\Delta t, \quad \Delta y/\Delta t = v. \quad \int_0^y y \Delta t = yt = \int_0^t (x_i + vt)\Delta t = x_i t + vt^2$$

$$y = x_i + at^2, \quad \Delta y = a\Delta t^2, \quad \Delta y/\Delta t^2 = a. \quad \int_0^y y \Delta t = yt = \int_0^t (x_i + at^2)\Delta t = x_i t + at^3$$

$$E = mv^2 = m(\Delta x^2/\Delta t^2), \quad \Delta E/\Delta x = m\Delta x/\Delta t^2 = ma. \quad \int_0^x F \Delta x = \int_0^x \frac{m\Delta x}{\Delta t^2} \Delta x = E$$

$$y = ke^x, \quad \Delta y/\Delta x = (k/\Delta x)e^{\Delta x}. \quad \int_0^x y \Delta x = yx = \int_0^x ke^x \Delta x = x ke^x$$

$$y = \ln x, \quad \Delta y/\Delta x = \ln \Delta x. \quad \int_0^x y \Delta x = yx = \int_0^x \ln \Delta x = x \ln x$$

$$y = A \sin(\omega t + \varphi), \quad \Delta y/\Delta t = (A/\Delta t) \sin(\omega \Delta t),$$

$$\Delta y/\Delta t^2 = (A/\Delta t^2) \sin(\omega \Delta t). \quad \int_0^t y \Delta t = yt = \int_0^t A \sin(\omega t + \varphi) \Delta t = A t \sin(\omega t)$$

SIMPLE OSCILLATION, WITH FRICTION AND FORCED OSCILLATION

As already noted, simple harmonic oscillation is,

$$y = A \sin(\omega t + \varphi), \quad \Delta y/\Delta t = (A/\Delta t) \sin(\omega \Delta t), \quad \Delta y/\Delta t^2 = (A/\Delta t^2) \sin(\omega \Delta t). \text{ And,}$$

$$\Delta y/\Delta t = (A/\Delta t) \sin(\omega \Delta t) = (A/\Delta t) \sin \omega(t_i - t_i) = (A/\Delta t) \sin \omega t_i \cos \omega t_i - \cos \omega t_i \sin \omega t_i.$$

¹ International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, Oct 2023-March 2024.

² >> >> >> >> >> >>, Oct 2020-March 2021

Here we must consider the initial conditions and define the initial time t_i , as $i = 0$. Then

$\Delta y/\Delta t = (A/\Delta t)\sin(\omega t_i)$, and because we do not consider final time, because it continues in the present, then,

$\Delta y/\Delta t = (A/\Delta t)\sin(\omega t)$. This is a consistent equation. In the same way,

$$\Delta y/\Delta t^2 = (A/\Delta t^2)\sin(\omega t).$$

And acceleration is a sine function, because when the speed of simple harmonic oscillation is large, then the acceleration is also great. Do not forget that $F=ma$ and a (the acceleration) are maximum at the center of the oscillation and vary according to the sine.

As you can see, we cannot make use of equations that hold in nature without resorting to initial conditions, Thus, we will have $y=Asin(\omega t+\phi)$ and initial condition $\phi=\pi/2$.

When there is friction in oscillators, such as ether friction, then $F=ma-bv=kx-bv=0$

$$x=x_0\sin(\omega t+\pi/2)=x_0\cos(\omega t), v=v_0\sin(\omega\Delta t) \text{ και } b=kx/v=k x_0\cos(\omega t)/v_0\sin(\omega\Delta t.) =C\cot(\omega t).$$

That is, as expected, the friction coefficient b varies like the cosine of oscillation times a constant C .

Now, if it is an external frequency, affecting oscillation, (forced oscillation), then $F=ma=ma_0-bv$. If we maintain the equality $ma=bv$, as indeed it does, then $ma_0=2ma=2bv$ (external force).

THE EQUATION OF STATE OF IDEAL GASES

As we know, under constant volume, the gas pressure is,

$$p=p_0(1+a\theta), \theta \text{ is the temperature of the gas in degrees Celsius and}$$

p_0 is the gas pressure at zero Celsius. And the volume under constant pressure is,

$$V'=V_0(1+a\theta).$$

So, under constant pressure,

$$pV= p_0(1+a\theta)V= p_0(1+a\theta)nV_0= np_0V_0(1+a\theta).$$

$$pV=nRT$$

This is the equation of state of ideal gases.

THE HYDROGEN ATOM

The³ centripetal force equation for the hydrogen atom is,

$$F = \frac{\mu_0 I_1 I_2 (2\pi R)}{2\pi R} = \mu_0 (e_m f)^2 = \frac{ke_m^2}{R^3} = kB e_m^2 \frac{0.4c^2}{R} = m \frac{0.4c^2}{R} = \frac{0.4(mcR)^2}{mR^3}$$

$$I_1=I_2=e_m f.$$

We know that $B=\mu_0 I/2\pi R$ and, $\mu_0=2\pi R B/I$. But we know from Balmer, $2\pi R=\lambda_0=91.1 \text{ nm}$, and $R=1.45 \times 10^{-8} \text{ m}$ (according to Balmer's formula). And,

$$\mu_0=9,11 \times 10^{-8} \text{ B/I}$$

Αλλά $\mu_0=0,4mc^2/R$ και,

$$m=3.3 \times 10^{-15} \text{ B/Ic}^2 = 3.67 \times 10^{-32} \text{ B/I.}$$

Και επειδή, $ke_m^2/R^3=\mu_0 I^2=\mu_0(e_m f)^2$

$$\mu_0=k3.03 \times 10^{-8},$$

αφού $f=c/\lambda_0=3.29 \times 10^{15} \text{ Hz}$. And,

$$B/I=3k$$

$$m=k1.1 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kgr}$$

$$e_m=1/f=3.03 \times 10^{-16} \text{ Cb}_m$$

³ THE NEW PHYSICS WITHOUT THE CONCEPT OF THE ELECTRIC CHARGE, International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, Oct.2023-Mar2024

and Cb_m = unit of quantity of magnetism.

True, $\frac{ke_m^2}{R^3} = m \frac{0.4c^2}{R}$ and, $k=1$

It holds, $ke_m^2/R^3 = \mu_0 I^2$ and, $I=1$ Amp, $B=3$ T.

The "electric" potential of one bubble is $V=ke_m/R^2=15.92$ Volts.

But in the hydrogen atom between the bubbles that roam,

$$F=e_m V/\pi R = ma = mR/(\Delta T/4)^2, \text{ because in } \Delta T/4 \text{ the force is exerted and}$$

$$V=(m/e_m)16R^2 /T^2(\pi)=(m/e_m)c^2(4/\pi)=13.6 \text{ Volt almost.}$$

This is the ionization tendency of the hydrogen atom in the Frank-Hertz experiment and is experimental proof of our theory.

THE e/m REASON THOMPSON FOUND

Thompson took a glass vacuum tube, as in the figure.

It had a thermionic cathode (cathode heated by the high current that passed). The cathode consisted of tungsten filament. As in sublimation here, a grain of ionized hydrogen atom consisting of the element Tungsten (all elements consist of hydrogen atoms and tungsten), was accelerated and deflected by the electric capacitor and magnets. He measured, as he said, the e/m ratio of the "electron", because he believed that the tungsten filament emitted electrons. He found $e/m=1.7588 \times 10^{11}$.

If we consider that the hydrogen grain had a mass $m_p=1.672 \times 10^{-27}$ kgr, as accepted by physics for the proton, and "charge" the magnetic quantity $e_m=3.03 \times 10^{-16} Cb_m$ that we found for the hydrogen atom, then the ratio is $e_m/m_p= 1.81 \times 10^{11}$, i.e. very close to Thompson's e/m.

So, the ionized grain of hydrogen atom measured in the Thompson experiment had the mass of the proton that standard physics accepts, but it has the charge that we found, and their ratio is what Thompson found experimentally.

Actually, they are $e/m=1.7588 \times 10^{11} = 3.03 \times 10^{-16} /m$ and $m=1.91 \times 10^{-27}$ kgr.

THE UNCHANGING POWER

Above we found, $\frac{ke_m^2}{R^3} = m \frac{0.4c^2}{R} = 9.1 \times 10^{-8} Nt$.

In the grain of the atom, at low pressure. $\frac{ke_m^2}{R^3} = m_k \frac{0.4v^2}{R}$

This force is the same when hydrogen is at 1 Atm pressure, where the mass is the same, but the charge is another. The charge was found by Millikan ($e=1.602 \times 10^{-19}$), so,

$$R=(ke^2/9.1 \times 10^{-8})^{1/3}=9.45 \times 10^{-11} m.$$

THE IMPERFECTIONS OF CREATION

As you know, there are diseases, death, parasitic microbes, earthquakes, wars, rape, theft, floods, hurricanes, erupting volcanoes, etc. There is evil.

We set as a principle in work, like Democritus and Epicurus, that there are atoms, indivisible the elementaries of hydrogen, in matter. Matter is structured by atoms, they are clusters of hydrogen atoms. So, we have to find the imperfections that start from them and evil is built into matter.

In atoms, such as hydrogen, we found that they have an energy E. We found for the hydrogen atom that it has $E = ke^2/R^2$ and an attractive force of the two charges (which as we showed are magnetic), $F=ke^2/R^3$.

There are mathematical series infinite, the sum of their terms equal to a unit. Such as,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{8} + \dots = 1$$

Then there is equality, $E=E_0 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n}$, $F=F_0 \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n}$

In reality, however, what the Lucifer created is the order,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{kn}}, \quad k > 1$$

The k from 1 constantly and long-term usually grows, so that energy and attractive force decrease, and wear and death occur.

Another factor of imperfection and the existence of evil in matter is the radial oscillation of the hydrogen atom. The two charges are distance R and this distance fluctuates, but the oscillation is not $R=R_i+R_0 \sin(\omega t + \phi)$, but is,

$$R=R_i+R_0 \sin(\omega t^k + \phi), \quad k > 1$$

As in the figure

$$R=3 \sin(2t^{1.2})$$

The energy of the radial oscillation is reduced and is combined with the decrease in the energy of the atom, indicated above.

EQUATIONS-OPERATORS FOR CREATING UNIVERSES, COMPLETING CREATION

$$x=x_0+v_x t, \quad y=y_0+v_y t, \quad z=z_0+v_z t$$

$$v_x=a_x t, \quad v_y=a_y t, \quad v_z=a_z t$$

$$x=x_0+ a_x t^2, \quad y=y_0+ a_y t^2, \quad z=z_0+ a_z t^2$$

$$E = \int_0^x F \Delta x = \int_0^x m a \Delta x = E = \int_0^x m \left(\frac{x}{t^2}\right) \Delta x = mv^2$$

$$F_c = 0.4m \frac{v^2}{r}$$

$$I=mv=c, \text{ with no force effect on } m$$

On circular motions, $S=m(rxv)=c$, without force effect on m

$$E=mgh=kmv^2$$

$E=mv^2$ for initial speed zero, exercise F in m.

$$E=Cx^2=mv^2 = , \text{ spring-loaded, small oscillations, } \int_0^x Cx \Delta x$$

$$E=E(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n})$$

$$F=kMm/r^3=m.04v^2/r,$$

$$r=r_i +r_0 \sin(\omega t+\phi)$$

$r=r_i +r_0 \cos(\omega t)$ and perpendicular to the orbit, $r'=r'_i +r_0' \cos(\omega t)$ and on the orbit,

$$r''=r''_i +r_0'' \cos(\omega t)$$

$$E= (\text{the mathematics we entered was used}). \int_0^r \frac{kMm}{r^3} \Delta r = \frac{kMm}{r^2} = mv^2$$

$$pV=nRT$$

$$E=(m/N)c\Delta T= m_A v^2$$

$$F-F'=F_{12}=-F_{21}=-F_x+F'_x$$

$$I=e/t=q/t$$

$$E=k(m/e)v^2$$

$$V=k(m/n^2 e^3)I^2$$

$$P=k(m/n^2 e^3)I^3$$

$$F = \frac{\mu_0 I_1 I_2 l}{2\pi r}$$

$$F = \frac{ke^2}{r^3}$$

$$r=r_i +r_0 \sin(\omega t+\phi)$$

$$F=I(l \times B)$$

$$F=e(v \times B)$$

$$m=kBe \quad F = \frac{ke^2}{r^3} = \mu_0 \frac{I^2(2\pi r)}{2\pi r} = \frac{0.4mv^2}{r}$$

$$E = \int_0^r \frac{ke^2}{r^3} \Delta r = \int_0^r \mu_0 \frac{I^2(2\pi r)}{2\pi r} \Delta r = \frac{ke^2}{r^2} = \mu_0 \frac{I^2}{1} = m_A v^2$$

$$V = \int_0^r \frac{ke}{r^3} \Delta r = \frac{ke}{r^2}$$

$$c=E/B$$

$$\text{Field of straight electrical conductor } B = \frac{\mu_0 I}{2\pi r}$$

$$\text{circular electric loop field, in its center, } B = \frac{\mu_0 I}{r}$$

All the above magnitudes and relationships are placed in equivocal correspondence with the corresponding relationships of our universes.

EPILOGUE

With new mathematics, where there will be no limit tending to zero, we are equipped to make the indicative equations-molds of creation of the 20 super-universes, without decay there. We achieve the avoidance of decay because we have diagnosed that it entered our universes, with an incomplete radial oscillation of the charged opposite particles of the atom and the incomplete infinite series that does not equal its sum to the unit and reduces the energy of atoms.

We moderate the equations of the harmonic oscillation. And the 20 superverses will have only harmonic oscillations.

The equations molded into the creation of universes are illustrative, and these universes will take thousands of years to form. Their atoms, were already created.

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